

Characterization of Delamination Failures in Glass Reinforced Plastics Ship Structures

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the mode of delamination failures of glass reinforced plastics (GRP) thick laminates is first classified and characterized which was observed in the damaged GRP large-sized fishing vessels due to impulsive wave loads. Then, the two kinds of special experimental techniques are proposed and examined in order to characterize the delamination resistance of GRP thick laminates under impulsive loading: a static and dynamic three-point bending test on a triple-notched specimen, and an impulsive delamination test on a Y-shaped specimen by an Izod impact tester. The former is effectively applied to discriminate the static and dynamic delamination toughness, while the latter is successful in evaluating the effect of laying-up time interval on the impulsive delamination toughness of GRP thick laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced plastics (GRP) has become to be widely accepted as construction materials for smaller fishing vessels in Japan during these twenty years. There had been no serious accidents in such GRP vessels before 1974, though the size of vessels had been becoming larger and larger. However, an extensive damage was noticed in forward bottom shells and double bottoms in about ten GRP large-sized fishing vessels during 1974 - 1976. The failure mode was observed to be mainly due to a marked delamination in GRP thick shell laminates. Hence the accidents motivated the reexaminations on materials, structures and fabrication methods in GRP large-sized ship construction technology in Japan (1, 2, 3).

This paper is concerned with the characterization of the delamination failure accidents in GRP large-sized fishing vessels mainly from the materials points of view. It is found noteworthy that GRP multilayered thick laminates are essentially susceptible to a delamination especially under impulsive loading, so that some special testing techniques are needed to evaluate the interlaminar strength, which is the weakest mode of strength, in GRP laminates (4). In the first half of this paper, the mode is characterized on the delamination failure accidents; in the second half, some special experimental techniques are described and examined to determine the relative interlaminar delamination toughness, instead of the interlaminar strength, of GRP thick laminates.

OUTLINE OF DELAMINATION FAILURE ACCIDENTS

The damage accidents happened in fourteen GRP bonito pole-and-line fishing vessels in which 13 vessels were 59 G.T. type and one was 49 G.T. type. Nine vessels were subjected to the accidents in the winter of 1974 - 1975, while five vessels were damaged in the winter of 1975 - 1976, during running at full speed on a rough sea when working in the southern fishing ground or returning to their homeports, which were located in various parts in the western region of Japan. The accidents arose independently of the passing of time after the construction, which was concentrated in two years from February 1973 to February 1975, in the damaged ships constructed by five of six shipyards which were the makers of this type of GRP fishing vessels at that time; some of which were damaged even at their maiden voyage.

Although the mode of damage was diversified, it is roughly classified into: (a) either a marked damage in floors and girders inside double bottoms, and a marked delamination in secondary bonded regions or not, (b) either a bored small hole or crack in outer bottom shells or not, (c) extensive delamination in outer shells from bilge to topside in 2 to 6 layers (outer shells: 10 to 14 plies) or local separated delamination; actually, the combined modes of (a), (b) and (c) were often observed. Figures 1 and 2 show typical examples in the locations and the sizes of extensive delamination in outer side and bottom shells in the damaged ships; Fig.3 shows a photograph of the appearance on delaminated forward bottom shell in a damaged ship.

Fig.1 Extensively delaminated area from bilge to topside in forward outer shell.

Fig.2 Delaminated and cracked area in forward bottom shell.

Notes: the symbols M(M') and R designate chopped strand mats and woven rovings, respectively, which are the most representative glass reinforcements in GRP ship constructions.

Fig. 3 Appearance on delaminated area in forward bottom shell.

Ship "A" (Starboard), Ship "B" (Port)

The outer shells were delaminated from the tank top to the forward upper side in the accommodation space in both cases. The laminate constitution of the outer shells is (from the outside surface):

GC + M450 + P80·60 x 5

where, GC: gel coat, M450: chopped strand mat (450 g/m^2), P80·60: combination of woven roving (800 g/m^2) and chopped strand mat (600 g/m^2). The failure mode is estimated as follows: the delamination occurred between R and M in the first layer, which started from the front edge of a lapped portion, while the the upper and lower edges propagated in the arbitrary directions stopping at another lapped portion. In the case of Ship "A", the front edge of a delaminated portion was such that a lapped layer was pulled out of upper and lower layers as shown in Fig.4.

The sequence of a delamination failure is estimated as follows (see Fig.4): the resin pockets lying intermittently around ① fails under an impulsive hydrostatic pressure losing the adhesive force; a delamination starts at ① propagating through the resin pockets and the voids which are scattered on the surface of woven roving layer ②. The gel coat and the backing M layer also break with ① as a starting point. When the interlaminar delamination at ② further proceeds, an overlay in the lapped portion is partially peeled causing a nonstop propagation of delamination due to a peeling force by a water current.

The estimated causes for the delamination failures are described from the viewpoints of ship structures as follows: the torsional rigidity is rather small at the forward accommodation space which lies between the rigid fish-hold space (containing a heat-prevention structure) and the bow (forming a triangle with outer shells and a bulkhead). The deep plate frames attached obliquely to the side shells (making a right angle to the centerline of the body) in the forward accommodation space are liable to fall when the outer shells are subjected to a large hydrostatic pressure, which reduces the stiffening effect of the frames. Consequently, a large torsion arises in the side shells causing a shearing force on the interface which drives a delamination to proceed together with a peeling force due to a water current. This is a typical example that a delamination occurred in outer

Fig. 4 A schema of delamination.

shells without any damage in double bottoms.

Ship "C"

A crack, 30 cm in length, was observed on the outer layer (M450) of the starboard bottom shell at the Frame Number 31 and another crack was also found at the intersection of the outer shells and the floors, which are regarded as just prior to developing into an interlaminar delamination. The laminate constitution of the outer shells is:

GC + M450 + (M600 + R810) x 4 + M600

When a thick GRP laminate is subjected to a large bending moment, a M layer on the tension side breaks first, while a R layer on the compression side is liable to buckle. If the load is repeated, the damage on the compression side grows possibly into a crack. If linearly-connected resin pockets lie in a lapped portion on the surface of outer shells, which is supposed to grow into a crack, it might be a starting point of interlaminar delamination. However, for an interlaminar delamination to proceed, it must be between R and M layers; because if there are only M layers, breaking easily into small pieces, it cannot be a large area; on the other hand, a R layer, fibers being continuous, can be delaminated in a large area.

Ship "D"

The side shell was delaminated over about 13 m in length starting from the damaged portion lying about 2.6 m ahead of the bilge keel on the port side. The laminate constitutions are:

GC + M450 + P80·60 x 4 (for the side shell)

GC + M450 + P80·60 x 2 (for the bilge keel)

As shown in Fig. 5, ① breaks due to a water impact, which was followed by the breaking of P inside ②, the remaining (M' + P) peeling the outer shell. As the port side was laid up from backward to forward, the lapped portions are successively peeled, which produces an extensive delamination.

Fig. 5 Bilge keel.

Ship "E"

The laminate constitution of the outer shells is:

GC + M450 + M600 + (MRM)

which was laminated with MRM as an unit: three layers of M, 3 m in width, were transversely laid up; five layers of R, 1 m in width, were longitudinally laid up; three layers of M, 2 m in width, were transversely laid up, either from the center toward fore and backwards. The failure is estimated to have occurred in the sequence: MMR was delaminated from the keel to near the upper deck, along 3 m in length backward from near the center of the forward accommodation space; MMR was further delaminated along 1.5 m in length from 1 m backward of the front edge of the previous delaminated zone; the remaining layers of the bottom shells break over 900 mm in length in the transverse direction at the back edge of the previous zone. The delaminated portions are observed to have started stepwise with the front edge as the lapped portions of woven rovings. The causes for the failures are regarded as almost same as above: the side shells being subjected to repeated torsion, the bottom to repeated bending due to wave impacts, a delamination started from the defects in the lapped portion and developed by a peeling force.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES FOR EVALUATING DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS

Although no test method has been established to evaluate the impact resistance of GRP, Charpy or Izod impact tests which are widely accepted in conventional metallic materials have often been applied to GRP. It is well known that the impact fracture surface in a notched GRP specimen is, however, greatly different from that of metal, because a crack tends to extend to a weaker interlaminar region being prevented by fibers to extend from a notch root. It is especially noteworthy that the impact often causes a considerable delamination in a GRP thick laminate. Sufficient discussions should be required on such peculiarity in the impact fracture mechanism of GRP, so that the conventional Charpy or Izod

impact values could be used as significant material comparison data of GRP.

It is observed that an interlaminar delamination is produced generally under a combined action of interlaminar shear and peeling. Hence it would be useful for evaluating the delamination toughness of GRP laminates if a pure interlaminar delamination could be generated under such a combined mode of stresses using a conventional Charpy or Izod impact tester. For this purpose, however, some considerations are required on the direction in which an impact force is applied to a specimen and on the configuration of notches in a specimen.

Charpy Impact Test on a Triple-notched Specimen

A simple test method is proposed in order to cause only an interlaminar delamination and no other mixed modes of fracture in a laminated specimen under bending. The method is based on a static and dynamic three-point bending with a span 60 mm of a triple-notched specimen as shown in Fig.6. The static test is performed with a crosshead speed 0.5 mm/min (8.3 $\mu\text{m/s}$) on an Instron-type testing machine; the dynamic test is performed with a striking velocity 3.8 m/s on a Charpy impact tester having a capacity of 150 kg $\cdot\text{cm}$.

A triple-notched specimen is broken into three pieces under Charpy impact, causing a complete delamination fracture between the two notches on the upper side of a specimen. No other mode of fracture than delamination is observed also under a static three-point bending, although some undelaminated portions remain, the area of which can, however, be determined after a test is finished.

Fig. 6 Configuration of a triple-notched specimen.

Although the static measurement of interlaminar strength itself would be unsuitable in this method because of a complex state of stresses around notches, the energy to delaminate a specimen can easily be determined by the area of a load-deflection curve in a static bending test and by the angle of rise of a pendulum in a Charpy impact test. The energy divided by the delaminated area is regarded as the static or dynamic absorbed delamination energy.

The static and dynamic delamination energies are compared on standard and Araton woven roving laminates as shown in Fig.7, in order to examine the effect of fiber surface treatments on the toughness of woven roving laminates. The specimens are standard and Araton-treated woven roving (600 g/m²) 15-ply laminates; the Araton treatment was developed by the Owens-Corning Fiberglas Co. to improve the wet-out performance of woven rovings.

Fig. 7 Comparison between absorbed delamination energy of standard and Araton-treated woven roving laminates.

In comparing the Araton woven roving laminates with the standard ones, the static absorbed delamination energy is about 60 % higher, while the dynamic one is about 10 % lower, as shown in Fig.7. The reason is considered to be as follows: the static delamination energy might be higher in the Araton laminates

than in the standard ones, because of the higher static interlaminar strength due to the improved wet-out performance; on the other hand, it may be estimated under a dynamic load that a delamination tends to proceed from a stronger interlaminar region to a weaker woven roving layer in the case of the standard laminates having the poorer wet-out performance, which is accompanied by considerable amount of fiber break and pull-out leading to a greater consumption of energy.

Although the testing method itself is simple, it is rather difficult to make a precise configuration of triple-notches in a specimen, so that the fracture mode may be scattered due to even a slight deviation in the locations of notch roots in a specimen; this is one of the main faults on this testing method.

Izod Impact Test on a Y-notched Specimen

A delamination is required to be generated at any prescribed interface in a laminated specimen, in order to make a significant comparative measurement on the interlaminar delamination toughness. For this purpose, an impulsive interfacial delamination test is devised in which an impulsive peeling force is applied on any prescribed interface in a GRP specimen using a standard Izod impact tester as shown in Fig.8. The impact point has a little offset over the delaminated plane, as shown in the figure, so that a peeling force is also applied together with an interlaminar shear, which makes it easy for a pure interlaminar delamination to start under a combined action of interlaminar shear and peeling.

The configurations of a proper test specimen has been examined on a single and double Y-notched specimens as shown in Fig.9 (a) and (b), respectively; a double Y-notched configuration is adopted here because it is found that a fracture cannot be avoided at the back edge of a holding jig in the case of a single Y-notched specimen. A Y-notch is cut in a specimen: a V-notch is first cut over 3 mm in depth, then a slit, 0.5 mm in width, is cut so that the total depth of a notch is 5 mm, in which the location of a slit is adjusted so that a delamination is forced to be generated on a prescribed interface of either R or M, as shown in Fig.9 (c).

Fig. 9 Configurations of Y-notched specimens:
 (a) single Y-notched;
 (b) double Y-notched;
 (c) detail of a Y-notch.

Fig. 8 Izod impulsive delamination test on a Y-notched specimen.

COMPARATIVE EVALUATIONS ON MOLDING CONDITIONS OF MR LAMINATES

The laying-up time schedule is important from the viewpoint of quality control in the hand lay-up molding of large-sized structures such as GRP ships, because the interlaminar bonding performance depends mainly on the chemical reaction of intermediate resin between layers which undergoes a change due to the passing of time. In molding a multi-layered large-sized structure with the combination of M and R layers, what is called "MR laminates", the laying-up cannot be completed within a short period, so that there is inevitably a certain amount of time interval between layer-to-layer laminations, ranging from "minute" or "hour" order (called "continuous lamination") to "day" order (called "intermittent lamination").

Hence the effects of laying-up time intervals should be properly evaluated on the interlaminar bonding performance of MR thick laminates in view of the interlaminar delamination resistance, which have, however, so far been neither qualitatively nor quantitatively clarified. For this reason, it is examined if there is any significant difference between observed impulsive delamination toughness on the above-mentioned Y-notched specimens of several kinds of MR laminates molded with varied laying-up time intervals. The test specimens are 18 kinds with the combination of the 3 kinds of laminate constitutions and the 6 kinds of molding cycles. The static bending and interlaminar shear strengths had been measured on these specimens which showed no significant difference.

Laminate constitutions (laying-up sequences): 3 kinds

Type A : (M-R)-(M-R)-(M-R)-(M-R)-(M-R)-(M-R)

Type B : (R-M)-(R-M)-(R-M)-(R-M)-(R-M)-(R-M)

Type C : (M-R-M)-(M-R-M)-(M-R-M)-(M-R-M)

where, M: chopped strand mat (600 g/m²), R: woven roving (860 g/m²), matrix: unsaturated polyester resin; inside the bracket: continuous lamination, between the brackets: intermittent lamination.

Molding cycles (laying-up time intervals): 6 kinds

Continuous lamination:

20 min [called "wet", symbol: M-R]; 3 hr [called "green", symbol: M=R]

Intermittent lamination:

1 day [called "dry", symbol:)-(]; 3 days [called "secondary bond", symbol:)=(); additional resin layer about 0.5 mm in thickness applied on secondary bonded interfaces [called "resin rich", symbol:)_{0.5t}(]

Although there are 34 kinds of interfaces in these 18 kinds of laminates with the combinations of basic parameters, the following fundamental 16 kinds of interfaces are selected for comparison (the mark "↓" designates the location of a prescribed interface):

MR interfaces: 7 kinds

-(M↓R)-, -(M=R↓)-, =(M↓R-M)=, =(M=R↓M)=; -M↓(R-, -M↓(R-; -M↓_{0.5t}(R-

RM interfaces: 7 kinds

-(R↓M)-, -(R=M↓)-, =(M↓R-M)=, =(M=R↓M)=; -R↓(M-, -R↓(M-; -R↓_{0.5t}(M-

MM interfaces: 2 kinds

-M↓(M-, -M↓(M-

The test results are summarized in Fig.10, in which the mean value of ten measurements and the range of mean ± standard deviation are shown for the 4 kinds of laying-up time intervals. In comparing the observed impact values as the impulsive delamination toughness at each prescribed interface, the followings are concluded:

MR interfaces: the toughness is greatest in wet-on-wet (20 min); the toughness is decreased in wet-on-green (3 hr), but is not decreased even in intermittent lamination (3 days).

RM interfaces: the toughness is greatest in wet-on-green, but is decreased in wet-on-wet; the toughness is furthermore decreased in intermittent lamination (3 days).

MM interfaces: significant difference is not observed, partly because MM interfaces are generally not so obvious in comparison to MR interfaces.

Resin rich layer: no significant effect is observed from these test results.

Fig.10 Comparison between impulsive interfacial delamination toughness at various prescribed interfaces.

CONCLUSIONS

It is clarified that an extensive delamination failure occurred probably under an impulsive loading between R and M layers in the outer shells of the typical damaged GRP large-sized fishing vessels. Hence it is important to evaluate the impulsive delamination resistance of MR or RM interfaces in MR laminates. For this purpose, the two kinds of modified Charpy and Izod impact tests are devised and proposed: a Charpy impact test on a triple-notched specimen and an Izod impact test on a double Y-notched specimen. The former is effective in discriminating the static and dynamic interlaminar delamination toughness, while the latter is successful in evaluating comparatively the impulsive delamination toughness at various prescribed interfaces in MR laminates. The comparative tests to examine the effects of molding cycles on the impulsive delamination toughness reveal that a standard laying-up procedure should be based on a repetition of wet-on-wet lamination of M-to-R, that is, (M+R)green, in view of the delamination toughness.

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